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ABSTRACT

This report presents the preliminary findings of the Schools against Fake News for a Cooler Future (SchoolFaN) project, which aims to combat the proliferation of climate change misinformation in Europe by equipping secondary school educators with innovative tools and strategies. Herein are presented the results from focus groups (FGs) conducted with teachers and teacher trainers in each country where they provided insights into their experiences, challenges, and needs regarding climate education and digital literacy. Qualitative analysis of FG data identified key themes related to curriculum gaps, teachers' readiness, and the role of citizen science in promoting critical thinking and engagement. Findings highlight the workload, the lack of time, resources and knowledge as the main barriers to promoting critical thinking and implementing a project on fake news in the classroom. As solutions, the participants pointed out the importance of working on a multidisciplinary and collaborative approach inside the schools, aligned with curricular goals and offering the teachers recognition. These results underscore the need for targeted professional development and educational resources to support teachers in cultivating a climate-aware, digitally literate generation. Recommendations for integrating these findings into school curricula and expanding support for teachers are provided.

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INTRODUCTION

The need to integrate global issues like climate change and digital literacy into European education is increasingly pressing. As the impacts of climate change intensify and online activity among youth grows, society becomes more vulnerable to misinformation, especially regarding scientific topics (Howard *et al.*, 2021). Misinformation about climate change is pervasive, distorting public understanding and undermining urgent climate action, especially among young people who frequently encounter unverified information online. To address this, students require foundational knowledge, digital skills and critical thinking to navigate critically and responsibly. Education systems, especially in Europe, must adapt to foster a new generation of informed, environmentally conscious, responsible individuals, and digitally literate individuals (European Commission, 2021; European Union, 2022).

The *Schools against Fake News for a Cooler Future* (SchoolFaN) project will help to address this issue. The project specifically seeks to (i) empower teachers in Portugal, Spain, France, and Greece to implement a citizen science approach in their classrooms to identify, analyze, and debunk climate-related fake news; (ii) foster secondary students' digital, scientific, and citizenship skills; and (iii) develop a scalable model for citizen science that can be adapted to other educational contexts. This project stands out for its cross-national approach, enabling a comparative analysis across four diverse European educational contexts. These countries were selected due to their unique vulnerability to climate-related misinformation, often exacerbated by local contexts and online discourse (Areia *et al.*, 2019). Secondary school students are at a critical age for developing critical thinking and environmental awareness, making secondary education a key phase for addressing climate-related misinformation. Moreover, and through a citizen science approach, the project seeks to provide actionable insights that inform the development of targeted resources, professional development opportunities, and curriculum guides. These tools aim to help teachers integrate topics such as global warming and digital literacy into their classrooms. By equipping teachers to guide students in identifying, analyzing, and debunking fake news related to climate change, the project promotes climate literacy and critical awareness. Citizen science, as an inclusive approach, engages students as active participants in scientific processes, encouraging

hands-on learning and empowering them to become agents of change (Roche *et al.*, 2020). Ultimately, this approach supports educators in shaping a generation that is environmentally conscious, digitally literate, and critically engaged with global challenges.

In order to integrate the citizen science project into the school curricula, we conducted focus groups with teachers and teacher's trainers in each of the participating countries. These focus groups provide an ideal method for gathering detailed qualitative data, capturing a diversity of perspectives and experiences (Morgan, 1996; Williams & Katz, 2001), designed to explore teachers' perceptions of the challenges they face when addressing climate change and misinformation in their classes and to identify promising contexts for implementing citizen science activities that debunk climate-related fake news. It offers a deeper understanding of the complexities of integrating topics like climate change and fake news into curricula while identifying good locations for citizen science activities related to fake news debunking. By bringing together educators and teacher trainers from different backgrounds and contexts, the focus group analysis will highlight common themes, shared challenges, and unique insights that other methods might not reveal.

METHODS

a. Study design

The methodology involved conducting focus groups (FGs) with secondary school teachers and teacher trainers from the four participating countries: Portugal (PT), Spain (ES), France (FR), and Greece (GR). These focus groups aimed to gather in-depth insights into the experiences, perceptions, and challenges that teachers and trainers face when addressing climate change and misinformation topics in their classrooms, particularly focusing on climate-related fake news, as well as determining ideal location of the curricula to address these issues.

The project follows the principle of participatory action research (PAR), a collaborative approach to conducting research and co-producing knowledge, such as by developing actionable recommendations (Buckles, 2019). This PAR framework facilitated the active involvement of teachers and trainers in the research process, allowing their expertise and experience to directly inform the project outcomes.

The approach employed a qualitative data collection method. To ensure consistency across the different countries, a moderator guide was developed to standardize the FGs processes in each location, as outlined in Appendix 1. The moderator guide included comprehensive guidelines for organizing the FGs, participant profile criteria, required documents, and an organizational checklist. The FGs guide also provided moderators with a detailed FGs script (Appendix 2), which structured the sessions into segments: a welcome/introduction, an icebreaker, an engagement question, seven exploratory questions, an exit question, and a final wrap-up including next steps. This structured approach ensured that all relevant aspects were explored systematically and in alignment with the research objectives.

b. Focus Groups (FGs) objectives

The FGs aimed to gather teachers' and teacher trainers feedback and validation on the following points:

- Integration of climate-related misinformation: Identifying where and how topics related to fake news on climate change are currently addressed in secondary school curricula.
- Citizen Science opportunities: Exploring ways in which citizen science initiatives aimed at combating climate misinformation could be integrated effectively within educational contexts in the participating countries.
- Preferred educational activities: Understanding the types of activities and resources that teachers would like to see developed to facilitate discussions on climate change and misinformation.

c. Selection criteria

Participants for the study were recruited on a voluntary basis, with focus groups (FGs) organized in each of the four participating countries — PT, ES, FR and GR. These FGs aimed to explore the perceptions, experiences, challenges faced, and needs of teachers and teacher trainers when addressing climate change and misinformation, particularly regarding climate-related fake news, in their classrooms, within the context of the project.

The participating teachers were selected through pre-existing contact networks established by the research institutes in each participating country. This purposive sampling approach prioritized teachers and teacher trainers primarily from natural sciences disciplines, including biology, geology, physics, chemistry, and geography courses for grades 9 through 12. To accommodate participants, we assessed the availability of interested teachers and arranged appointments at mutually convenient times, maximizing attendance. The target sample size was 5 to 8 participants per FGs (Krueger and Casey, 2000; Plummer-D'Amato, 2008), ensuring a manageable group size that would foster active engagement and allow each participant to contribute meaningfully to the discussion.

d. Participant profile

Teacher Trainers:

Two teacher trainers were included in each FGs. Eligible trainers could be university professors teaching in Pedagogical Departments (undergraduate or postgraduate levels) or qualified teachers with experience in teacher training. Trainers might also work as freelancers conducting teacher training programs for private or public institutions.

In-Service Teachers:

Each FG included four in-service teachers with 5 to 10 years of experience, covering subjects such as biology, geology/geography, physics, and chemistry. The teachers represented various grade levels:

- o **9th grade** :General natural sciences, including biology, geology/geography, physics, and chemistry.
- o **10th, 11th, and 12th grades**: Scientific branch subjects, with a focus on biology, geology/geography, physics, and chemistry.

Diversity and Inclusion:

Gender equality and diversity were prioritized in the selection process. An inclusion criterion required that participants acknowledge climate change as a scientifically validated fact. During recruitment, candidates were asked, “Do you recognize climate change as supported by scientific evidence?” to verify alignment with this prerequisite.

In total, there were 25 participants in the FGs, 14 teachers, 9 teacher trainers and 2 undefined participants (marked with § in Table 1): 3 teachers and 2 teachers trainers in Portugal; 4 teachers and 2 teachers trainers in Spain; 3 teachers, 3 teachers trainers and 2 undefined participants in France; and 3 teachers, 1 teacher trainer, 1 lab teacher trainer, 1 teacher consultant in Greece (Table 1).

e. Data collection

The FGs were conducted via videoconference in June and July 2024 and were planned to take between 60 and 90 minutes. The duration varied slightly between countries, ranging from 1h in Greece, 1h30 in Portugal and 1h45 in Spain¹. All sessions were recorded directly through the videoconferencing platform to facilitate accurate transcription and data analysis.

At the beginning of each FG, the moderator, responsible for leading the session, clarified the session's objectives, managed group dynamics, monitored timing, and ensured all participants understood the recording process. Before starting, the moderator obtained verbal consent from each participant to record the session. During the FGs, the moderator also took notes on elements that required further clarification, ensuring comprehensive data collection.

Following each FG session, the project team summarize key ideas presented and discuss considerations relevant for subsequent phases of the study.

f. Data analysis

Each FG was transcribed verbatim into a separate Word document by the project team in each participating country, that were then translated into English and checked for accuracy to enable a consistent analysis across all research teams. The transcription process was conducted promptly after each FG to ensure the accuracy and retention of main points.

The data analysis process followed a **six-phase approach**:

1. **Familiarization with the dataset:** Four members of the NOVA team engaged in reading and re-reading of the transcripts to familiarize themselves with the data. This process occurred over

¹ Information regarding France has to be confirmed.

several sessions, with varying combinations of team members, allowing for diverse perspectives and the generation of initial analytic ideas across all FGs.

- 2. Coding:** In accordance with Boyatzis 1998 guidelines, we adapted our coding approach to align with the research question, maintaining openness to unexpected themes. Qualitative data were coded and categorized through thematic analysis using the MAXQDA software, which involved labeling text segments directly from the participants' own words. This approach generated a substantial number of coded segments, offering a detailed foundation for further analysis. In addition to inductively generated codes, the PISA 2025 (OECD, 2023) and DigiComp (Vuorikari et al., 2022) frameworks were used as references to guide and inspire our categorization and interpretation of participants' observations and remarks, particularly concerning the integration of climate change and digital literacy into the curriculum. This approach enabled us to evaluate how competencies from these frameworks—such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and digital literacy—were reflected in teachers' inputs (see Table 3: Codes).
- 3. Generating initial themes:** In this phase, we identified patterns of shared meaning across the dataset by clustering related codes. This fusion process allowed us to observe emergent themes within the data, moving beyond individual codes to broader patterns.
- 4. Developing and reviewing:** Here, we reviewed the initial themes by revisiting the full dataset, assessing each theme's relevance and alignment with existing knowledge in the field. During this stage, we applied deductive categorization, organizing the themes into the initial framework of 23 categories and 71 sub-categories.
- 5. Refining, defining and naming:** Each theme was refined and clearly defined, with concise descriptions added to capture their essence and analytic relevance.
- 6. Writing up analytical narratives:** In the final phase, we crafted analytical narratives for each theme, supported by illustrative data extracts.

g. Ethics approval

The study protocol received ethical approval from different countries - the Ethics Committee of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA), on 28.06.2024, under file number 174/2024; and Rey Juan Carlos University (URJC), on 10.05.2024, under file number 120420242522024 in the case of Spain. All participants provided informed consent prior to participation, ensuring their understanding of the study's objectives, procedures, and data handling policies.

To protect participant confidentiality, all data were pseudonymized during the transcription process. Each participant's identity was replaced using a standardized coding format, where a combination of letters and numbers (e.g., "P1" for "Participant 1") was used to denote individual contributors. This pseudonymization process aligns with data protection regulations and best practices for safeguarding participant anonymity throughout the analysis and reporting phases.

Table 1. Sociodemographic data (n = 27) distributed over 4 groups, one in each participating country.

Participant	Country	Subject	Category	Experience (Years)	Group (total)
P1	Spain	Physics-chemistry	Teacher Trainer	30	Group 1 (n=7)
P2		Biology-Geology	Teacher Trainer	25	
P3		Biology-Geology	Teacher	6	
P4		Biology-Geology	Teacher	23	
P5		Geography	Teacher	16	
P6		Physics-chemistry	Teacher	34	
P7		Biology-Geology	§	§	
P8	France	Biology-Geology	Teacher Trainer	33	Group 2 (n=8)
P9		Biology-Geology	Teacher	15	
P10		Biology-Geology	Teacher	33	
P11		Biology-Geology	§	§	
P12		Physics-chemistry	Teacher Trainer	9	
P13		Physics-chemistry	Teacher	9	
P14		Physics-chemistry	Teacher Trainer	15	
P15		Biology-Geology	Teacher	15-20	
P16	Greece	Biology Physics-	Teacher	20+	Group 3 (n=6)
P17		Chemistry Biology	Head of School	20+	
P18		Biology lab	Teacher Trainer	15-20	
P19		Geology-Physics	Teacher Trainer	15-20	
P20		Physics-Chemistry	Teacher Consultant	15-20	
P22		Physics-chemistry	Teacher Trainer		
P23	Portugal	Biology-Geology	Teacher	INQ	Group 4 (n=5)
P24		Geography	Teacher		
P25		Geography	Teacher		
P26		Geography	Teacher Trainer		

§ Franceundefined participants; INQ – InformationNotRequested

RESULTS: KEY FINDINGS

a. Critical thinking in the classroom

The issue of **whether the school curricula empower or not students' critical thinking** was **not unanimous** among the four focus groups and within the groups themselves. Among the participants from Spain, there was a widespread perception that curricula do not promote students' critical thinking. On the other hand, France's teachers generally believe that critical thinking is promoted in curricula. Opinions were mixed and divided in the other two groups, Portugal and Greece.

There was a generalized idea among the participants from all groups that critical thinking is present and highlighted within the student's profile, the curricula for each subject, and educational guidelines. In addition, the teachers mentioned that deconstructing information and connecting everyday problems with the knowledge acquired in classes is increasingly valued in education. However, there was also the perception that the implementation depended on each teacher's work and strategy. These were the

barriers and difficulties discussed that prevent teachers from promoting critical thinking in the classroom:

- **Length of the curriculum and the workload**
Teachers need more time dedicated to activities that engage and explore critical thinking and scientific literacy. The curriculum presents the topics, but the time to work on them in depth needs to be increased. These professionals feel suffocated by the length of the curriculum and the goals they must meet every year.
- **Lack of resources and know-how**
The participants highlighted a need for more resources, means, and knowledge to implement this task. Promoting critical thinking is a longitudinal, continuous process that has to be worked on over the years (e.g., bringing weekly news to encourage critical thinking). Furthermore, constant updates from the teachers are required.

- **Outdated curricula and manuals**

Another pointed issue is that school manuals/curricula are old, limited and unable to present the topics in a cohesive and updated way (e.g. in some disciplines, climate change is not present in the curricula, or the concept of the climate crisis is not mentioned).

- **Socioeconomic and cultural differences**

There is a clear distinction between students who have access to information and students who are conditioned by geographic and knowledge barriers or who have more difficulty understanding specific terminologies and who also have less economic power to be able, for example, to acquire dictionaries or extra classes.

- **The power of social media**

Students often consume everything they are shown and may believe everything on social media (e.g., information from TikTok or YouTube) is true. Greater credit and veracity are given to social networks than websites, blogs and the teacher's lessons.

- **Memorization vs. critical thinking**

This critical thinking is often confused and analyzed as memorization. Students simply memorize without understanding in order to obtain good grades.

For example, they are focused on identifying the cause and effect of phenomena like chemical reactions without considering the impacts it could have on the environment.

To overcome these difficulties, the participants proposed some **ideas and solutions**. In particular:

Promoting critical thinking in students could be addressed in courses with greater curricular autonomy, such as Citizenship or Citizenship Education/Science Teaching/ Digital Teaching. In addition, doing so within horizontal and **multidisciplinary networks** of teachers and educators from different areas (not only exact sciences) would enrich the process. Teachers also point out that there is a greater appeal for a more practical and integrated view of the knowledge.

Another suggestion was to work on **the student/teacher dipole**. This relationship must be the focus of the government and of the scientific community so that the message can be transmitted, solutions can

be found, and behaviors changed. Also, promoting debates among students, while teaching them to debate and to differentiate accurate and inaccurate information, could be a vital tool for empowering critical thinking.

Finally, some teachers suggested that critical thinking could be addressed within particular curricular topics, indicating climate change as a possibility. One of the most paradigmatic examples was the **greenhouse effect**, a topic that in curricula is currently described as essential for life on earth, but teachers still have to deconstruct old misconceptions. There is still the idea that carbon dioxide and the greenhouse effect are bad and harmful and that its only cause is anthropogenic, and it is up to the teachers to work on a more critical, global and informed vision.

b. Fake news on the curricula

Most teachers do not feel comfortable or **feel they do not have enough knowledge to address the topic of fake news** in class. Still, some teachers sought to develop skills through a workshop where

they learned to identify and classify science videos in terms of respect for their reliability and veracity. Also, some teachers mentioned projects entirely dedicated to fake news promoted by the school library.

Some situations were mentioned as opportunities the teachers have used to address fake news in class, particularly:

- The greenhouse effect, previously mentioned, was also used as a way to introduce fake news examples. When asked for fake news addressed in their classes, the participants gave the example of the ozone layer, which is often confused with the greenhouse effect. Some news about the ozone layer say that the ozone hole was getting bigger when, in fact, it is the layer that is getting thinner. This was mentioned in an example about a debate on Al Gore's documentary "An Inconvenient Truth" (2006), and an exploration in the classroom of a set of fake news that came out at the time.

- In line with this, some teachers use statements from public figures (such as politicians or comedians) to promote discussion and address climate change. As striking examples, we highlight the tweets of Donald Trump (an American politician), the statements by Lakis Lazoupolos (a Greek comedian) about the greenhouse effect, and the theory that Margaret Thatcher was responsible for climate change.
- The COVID-19 pandemic was also a mentioned source of fake news related to health and to a lot of misinformation. Even though there was nothing planned, the teachers took advantage of the momentum and the fake news that were constantly published to address the issue.
- Lastly, another highlight was the use of artificial intelligence to produce fake news materials (e.g. The teachers would use ChatGPT to create fictitious values for laboratory chemistry protocols or several titles of fake and real historical events and would ask the students to discover the differences).

The specific points of the curricula that the teachers considered adequate to address fake news associated with climate change are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Summary of focus group about the points of the curricula that are adequate to address fake news associated with climate change.

SUBJECT	SCHOOL YEAR	CONNECTION TO CURRICULUM	COMMENTS
FRANCE			
Biology and Geology	10th grade	Biodiversity (the last part is the impact of man in biodiversity)	Teachers have included projects on climate change in the biodiversity section).
	12th grade	Past and future climates	
Digital teaching	10th grade	Social networks Social media	One teacher mentions activity on fake news developed in digital teaching in collaboration with the librarian. Teachers think there many points of convergence in digital teaching with fake news.
EMC (moral and civic education)	Secondary school	Information channels	There was no EMC teachers present in the focus group, but it was pointed out that there are possibly things to do with fake news and the climate.
History and Geography	Middle school	Environmental topics	
	Secondary school		No specific topic was indicated.
Physics and Chemistry	No specific school year was indicated	Technologies (allows looking into global warming) Energy (allows looking into climate and some environmental issues)	
	10th grade	Teaching in a foreign language	Teaching in a foreign language in the 10th grade has a very free curricula.

	12th grade	Renewable energies and climate change	
Scientific Teaching	10th, 11th and 12th grade	Critical thinking	
		How science is constructed	
	12th grade	Global warming Climate	
GREECE			
No subject was specified	No specific school year was indicated	No specific school year was indicated	<p>The curriculums are going to change, so the teachers could not clearly point out specific points of the curricula.</p> <p>Suggestion: Relate to actual examples: fires in Greece, extreme snowfall, the very high temperatures in the summer, the intense floods.</p> <p>"One general objective of the curriculum is to use the knowledge acquired by students to develop critical thinking towards contemporary phenomena, to connect them with events in their daily lives."</p>
Biology	no school year specified	Positive aspects of the greenhouse effect.	
		Intensive extraction and combustion.	
	10th and 11th		Suggestion: experimental activities that lead to the production of carbon dioxide (showing how the temperature increases depending the concentration of carbon dioxide).
Chemistry	9th and 10th	Factors that affect the climate.	
		Our civilization has relied on combustion.	

		Book mentions that in recent years the use of fossil fuels has continued to increase.	
Geology-Geography			The curriculum states that "children should understand that the environment is not static."
PORTUGAL			
			Teachers suggestions: -to include the project in the context of a science club. -to integrate the project within an interdisciplinary projects, at the level of curricular autonomy domains.
Biology-Geology	10th grade	Geology section Earth system and the interactions between systems	
	11th grade	Biology - Evolution Geology (resources associated with environmental protection and protection of resources)	
	12th grade	Human biology	
Citizenship and Development		Possibility to explore media literacy, environmental literacy, etc. Possibility to relate to entrepreneurship.	In some schools, this course is transversal. There are mandatory topics and there are additional topics that can be developed. Teacher suggestion: include as an assignment in biodiversity.
Geography	7th grade	Climates at a global level	
	9th grade	Environment and society Decrease in the thickness of the ozone layer	
	Secondary	Environment	
	10th grade	Climate in Portugal	

		Dynamics of the coastline and the increase in the average sea level	
	11th grade	Agriculture	
	12th grade (Geography C)	Society	
Natural Sciences	7th grade	Major extinctions (could connect to environmental problems associated with climate change)	The connections are more indirect.
	8th grade	Climate, the atmosphere and the various parts of the Earth system. Pollution Biology and Geology section Case studies about Portugal Global warming and the consequences of global warming. Environmental pollution, deforestation and human influence on the environment (essential learning point)	The 8th grade curriculum is very good for working on any type of environmental connection: deforestation, species conservation, diversity, etc. In addition, the curriculum is relatively small.
	9th grade	Respiratory system Individual and community health (environmental implications for health)	The connections are more indirect.
Physics-Chemistry	10th grade	Atmosphere composition and its layers	More difficult to address in the 9th grade because the curriculum focuses on the periodic table.
	11th grade	Acid-base (includes acid rain and the release of polluting gases into the atmosphere) Solubility in water (can address acid rain)	Including in the 11th grade has the problem of having the national exams at the end of the school year.
	12th grade	Align directly or indirectly with metals and organic compounds.	There is “total freedom” in 12th grade).
SPAIN			
No subject was specified	No specific school year was indicated	No specific school year was indicated	Teachers suggestion: to Integrate the project transversally in sustainability.

			<p>To introduce at any level, as this is an emergency situation.</p> <p>Fake news and its relationship with climate change should be introduced using a competency approach.</p> <p>Mention to the site: https://maldita.es/</p> <p>Teachers have made a transversal project about climate change joining biology + geography + history c.</p>
	4th year of ESO		Teacher has developed a project in a diversification group (lower level, less students per group, closer teaching).
Biology and Geology	ESO (4 years of Educación Secundaria Obligatoria)		Sustainability. Ecology and evolution.
	1st year of high school	Scientific project section	(one of the competencies and criteria is reliable sources).
	3rd year of ESO 4th year of ESO		The students at this point have enough maturity and some knowledge.
	No specific school year was indicated	Human Biology Impact on health of climate change Sustainable food Health	Teachers suggest possible links in: distribution patterns of disease-transmitting mosquitoes, heat waves, extreme events like floods; fake news related to health; and to plants engineered to adapt to climate change.

		Genetic engineering Scientific Culture Environment	
Biology, Geology and Environmental Sciences	Highschool		It is in the curriculum, and it is easier to work with students this age. Suggests to introduce climate change and work on the fake news of climate change.
Geography	1st year of ESO	Characteristics that allow life on the planet Biosphere	As the students are younger, if the project is included in this level, the teachers would have to be the ones to create that search or make them search for that news.
	4th year of ESO	Earth and universe block Habitability conditions	In this level it would be a good time — it would reach more students and at this age the students have higher capabilities, abilities to do research and a critical mind.
Geology	No specific school year was indicated	Evolutionary history	
Language	No specific school year was indicated	No specific topic was indicated	The language class provides an opportunity to develop this project; the project could be developed transversally.
Physics and Chemistry	4th year of ESO	Energy and heat	The teacher has previously developed a project on climate change.
	High school (in first and second high school)	Thermochemistry Energy and Chemistry	
	First high school and second high school		
	Second grade	Uniting biology and geology in physical and chemical properties of water	

Note: This table includes mostly answers from question #4 where teachers are asked about the points in the curriculum that would be adequate to address fake news related to climate, but also includes contributions from question #2 (where teachers are asked about addressing fake news in class) and from question #3 (where teachers are asked about addressing climate change in class).

Table 3. Qualitative data codification.

CATEGORY	SUBCATEGORY	SUBCATEGORY DEFINITION	EXAMPLES OF TEACHERS ANSWERS	NUMBER OF THE TIMES MENTIONED (N)	
General Perception	Curriculum Empowerment	Positive sentiment	Feedback indicating that the curriculum is perceived as empowering	"Are you asking whether the curriculum and programs encourage students to have a critical mind and to be critical of the information they consume? I think that, in general, yes" FG Portugal	10
		Negative sentiment	Perceptions that the curriculum does not empower students	"Yes, in Biology, there are fragmented and sometimes contradictory references in the curricula regarding climate change. Elsewhere they are referred to as climate change, elsewhere as climate change, elsewhere as possible consequences and impacts of climate change... They spread some doubt in this way. And I think that generally, the curricula reflected in the books used today do not help towards the direction of the question you posed." FG Greece	11
		Mixed sentiment	Varied views, where some aspects of the curriculum are seen as empowering while others are seen as limiting	"Yes, in fact, one thing, trying in with that in biology and geology we have the scientific project section and one of the competencies and criteria is reliable sources. Teach them to detect reliable sources of information. In other words, at least, it is now a little more directly expressed." FG Spain	1
Specific Elements of the curriculum	Critical Thinking skills	Explicit teaching	Specific, structured instruction dedicated to critical thinking development.	"What I try to do is, through the lens of geological history, show them that the climate changed anyway on Earth. And in earlier geological eras, we had significant climate changes. I just try to show them that now it might be happening very quickly and uncontrollably." FG Greece	7
		Lack of instruction	Absence of structured lessons or content aimed explicitly at building critical thinking.	"But I think that many times we stay only in the learning of cause-effect and we do not debate much about these aspects." FG Spain	9
		Integration across	Embedding critical thinking	"To a large extent, I used the material that is taught. That is, for example, that forests absorb carbon dioxide, so there is	2

Specific Elements of the curriculum		subjects	practices across various subject areas to reinforce skill development.	some balance with what is produced from respiration or some combustions. The books mention (maybe not in biology, but in chemistry) that in recent years, the use of fossil fuels has continued to increase, the combustion of fossil fuels." FG Greece	
	Media Literacy	Inclusion	Efforts to integrate media literacy as part of the curriculum to enhance students' critical interpretation of media.	"Yes, I'd mentioned it, but I wasn't the one working on it, it was the school librarian who's been doing a lot of work on fake news for years. She could talk to you better than I could about the fact that, in their day-to-day lives, they are inundated with fake news." FG France	1
		Absence	Absence of media literacy in the curriculum.	"One of the activities that came from this classroom check was one of the images created with artificial intelligence and there was one of the Dad and it was to see if they were able to discern if it was true or not. And most of them fell." FG Spain	4
		Practical exercises	Hands-on media literacy activities that encourage students to practice analyzing media critically.	"So I'm working in particular on the results of the first research on Covid and how it worked. We start from this and then work on articles found on the internet. We look at what allows us to see the extent to which the article is completely false, or even just to have a point of view on the reliability of the evidence provided." FG France	4
		Training	Programs instructional methods to teach students to assess the credibility, reliability, and relevance of sources.	"In fact, we redefine with them the terms of what is news, fake news, a hoax and so on, so that they are familiar with the different terms and then it's up to them to work together to verify the information." FG France	3
	Source Evaluation	No training	Absence of specific training on source evaluation skills.	"It was a bit of a scary experience for me, because I was expecting the students to get there in 2 minutes and for the class to be over because someone would quickly raise the issue that the information didn't make sense and that the data wasn't correct." FG Portugal	1
		Encouragement of questioning sources	Promoting a mindset of inquiry where students are encouraged to question information	"So I'm working in particular on the results of the first research on Covid and how it worked. We start from this and then work on articles found on the internet. We look at what	3

Specific Elements of the curriculum			sources.	allows us to see the extent to which the article is completely false, or even just to have a point of view on the reliability of the evidence provided. So we're working on vocabulary to find out where things stand." FG France	
	Current Events Discussion	Use for critical analysis	Using current events discussions as a tool to develop students' critical thinking and analytical skills by connecting classroom concepts to real-world issues.	"We take a tweet Donald Trump made a few years ago about global warming and we can ask the pupils what they think or exchange views. That's one of the things we've been trying to put in place." FG France	3
Teaching Strategies	Interactive learning	Use of interactive methods	Employing active, student-centered approaches like group work and discussions to foster engagement and deeper learning.	"... through the "skills labs," because I had the luck to conduct a skills lab for some years, there is an entire axis for climate change and the climate crisis with very nice activities." FG Greece	7
		Reliance of traditional methods	Predominant use of conventional, lecture-based methods that may limit student critical interaction and engagement.	"So, I will mainly speak about the textbook because, let's face it, the textbook is our guide in the classroom, regardless of what is mentioned in the curriculum." FG Greece	2
		Student engagement in activities	Predominant use of conventional, lecture-based methods that may limit student interaction and critical engagement.	"And, on my own, in scientific culture, two years ago, I did show you some videos of detecting fake news from those at malasditamaldita.es, I think they have some informative video on the subject, some TED videos on pseudotherapies, to work on, so that they could see, that they alone could deduce, if that could be real or not." FG Spain	2
	Project-based learning	Implementation	Structured integration of projects to provide hands-on, learning inquiry-based experiences.	"Last year, another of those extinct in the Community of Madrid, in Applied Anatomy I did an activity on aesthetic canons. So, of course, I proposed to them, well, the aesthetic canons. So I told him what I had prepared, and my own bias, right? From Western society... But then I blurted out: "And do you know that in Japan...?" Go now! We gave each student a	2

Teaching Strategies				culture or a society and they had to analyze there to see that there were things that they would have believed to be false or that they would not have believed at the time." FG Spain	
		Lack of opportunities	Limited or absent project-based learning opportunities, restricting experiential learning potential.	"Nothing, for my part I have not had any, come on, I have not developed any specific activity on fake news." FG Spain	1
		Effectiveness in teaching	Structured integration of projects to provide hands-on, learning inquiry-based experiences.	"Yes, in fact, one thing, tying in with that in biology and geology we have the scientific project section and one of the competencies and criteria is reliable Teach them to detect reliable sources of information. In other words, at least, it is now a little more directly expressed." FG Spain	2
Teacher Preparedness and Support	Teacher Training	Adequate	Adequate teacher training focused on equipping educators to promote critical thinking skills.	"Well, I have participated in some workshops in this regard, because it is a topic that interests me quite a bit., about fake news and kids, and the person who previously coordinated came to give us a workshop SYNC, the scientific news website. It was called Pampa, Pampa.... I don't remember and he gave us a workshop in class to teach them how to detect fake news. Although it focused a lot on WhatsApp and caught them a little out of hand, but oh well." FG Spain	2
		Inadequate	Inadequate teacher training for critical thinking.	"But it was something that we here inside fabricated to try to understand whether, in fact, the teachers understood, and I have to tell you that many did not understand and consumed the data as if it were correct and real. And it was interesting when we gave the real data, since before we had fake data." FG Portugal	4
Student Outcomes	Student Engagement	High	Observable high levels of interest, motivation, and participation from students in learning activities.	"I mean, what I did was take it to the classroom and they did like it." FG Spain	1
		Low	Limited student engagement or classroom enthusiasm in	"But the children are just terrified and ultimately indifferent." FG Greece	1

Student Outcomes	Student Skills		activities, suggesting potential barriers to motivation.		
		Development of critical thinking skills	Fostering students' abilities to think critically, reason logically, and approach problems analytically.	"And it is often this power of abstraction that they also lack and that through these images, and even some three-dimensional images, they can understand more easily." FG Portugal	2
		Lack of critical thinking skills	students' challenges or deficiencies in critical thinking abilities.	"So they don't even have the ability to question themselves: this can't happen, this isn't true. They consume everything that comes their way and that is very, very, very worrying." FG Portugal	7
Barriers and Challenges	Curriculum Limitations	Constraints of the existing curriculum	Structural limitations within the curriculum that restrict comprehensive teaching and learning, especially in critical thinking.	"I think it becomes difficult. In other words, I think that, on the ground, not many activities are developed with the need to move forward with the curriculum. The length of the curriculum is such that we end up not dedicating more time to activities that would be necessary to make students more critical and involved. I believe that this could be done more easily within the scope of the strategy for citizenship and education for citizenship, areas of curricular autonomy with other subjects." FG Portugal	17
		Recommendations for improvement	Suggestions or proposals aimed at enhancing the curriculum to better support critical thinking and adaptability	"Therefore, to articulate all of this, it would be necessary for teachers to have a more integrated vision of the content, for example in projects. Another way would be for the Ministry itself to have this vision and integrate projects, which is something that does not happen." FG Portugal	6
	External Influences	External misinformation	Effects of false or misleading information from outside sources, impacting students' understanding and critical thinking.	"So now that is also another challenge, artificial intelligence between the created texts and the created images, because we have it even more difficult." FG Spain	3
		Parental/community influence	Influence of parents or community beliefs on students' attitudes, potentially shaping their perspectives and critical	"And obviously we have regions of the country where the population has access to other resources, but especially in the interior, where we have a population where families cannot afford to pay for tutoring and where many people do	1

Barriers and Challenges			skills.	not even have dictionaries at home, it is very difficult for students to understand certain terminology used when addressing this topic and this requires more work on our part." FG Portugal	
		Social media	The impact of social media platforms on students' perceptions and information consumption habits.	"I have students in the 11th grade who say: "But I saw it on Tiktok". So their base is now very much Tiktok. "OK, fine, you saw it on Tiktok, so what?" "If it's on Tiktok, it happened, it's true". FG Portugal	4
Fake news Origin	Format	Text	"Many years ago, more than a decade, a student mentioned a piece of news that I had also read." FG Greece	"Many years ago, more than a decade, a student mentioned a piece of news that I had also read." FG Greece	5
		Video	"For example, Lazopoulos, the well-known actor, mentioned in one of his shows, watched by tens of thousands of people, that the greenhouse effect is due to the ozone hole." FG Greece	"For example, Lazopoulos, the well-known actor, mentioned in one of his shows, watched by tens of thousands of people, that the greenhouse effect is due to the ozone hole." FG Greece	4
	Media		Traditional sources of news such as newspapers, TV news channels, and radio, used as primary sources of information.	"For example, Lazopoulos, the well-known actor, mentioned in one of his shows, watched by tens of thousands of people, that the greenhouse effect is due to the ozone hole." FG Greece	10
	Social media		Platforms like TikTok, Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube used by students and teachers to access and share information.	"But just what I'm thinking is that the main source of all this fake news is YouTube. I've heard it referred to as the largest educational platform. Of course, the quality of the education it provides is a big issue." FG Greece	3
Educational Benefits	Curriculum integration		The alignment of projects with the existing curriculum, facilitating smooth	"The issue of the curriculum, I think, is also very important because obviously the smaller the gap between the curricular objectives and the project objectives, the greater the sense of	4

Educational Benefits		implementation and relevance to subject areas.	commitment and the perceived usefulness of the project." FG Portugal	
	Skill and Competencies development	Focused efforts on building students' practical skills and competencies beyond traditional academic knowledge.	"I think a good idea, which was mentioned earlier, is the skill workshops, which are essentially taken on by individuals who are interested, there is no specific curriculum for the teacher to cover, there are only some activities." FG Greece	9
	Student Engagement and motivation	Strategies to increase students' interest and enthusiasm for learning, promoting active participation.	"I think that's something that would be very motivating for teachers and for their pupils." FG France	5
	European Context	Consideration of the European educational framework or policies influencing curriculum design and teaching strategies.	"We found the exchange between young people from different EU countries really interesting. How climate change was perceived in their countries, Northern Europe/Southern Europe, and then how to find solutions in everyday life." FG France	6
Teacher benefits	Professional development	Opportunities for educators to enhance their knowledge, skills, and professional growth through training and workshops.	"Research will usually result in scientific publications, books, articles, and so what role can I play as a co-author of all this? I think this could be an interesting element. How do I participate in the construction of scientific knowledge?" FG Portugal	2
	Networking Opportunities	Platforms or events that allow teachers and students to connect with peers, share ideas, and collaborate.	"Obviously, there are scientists, research laboratories, other spaces, and other contexts that are often not those that appear in so-called non-citizen science projects. I think that this can also be an aspect that makes the project appealing, that is, I can have scientists who are more involved in schools. Teachers and students can also go to universities and research centers. I think that this permeability that is created in the citizen science project, with other spaces and other interlocutors, should also be an element that should be put on the table and that may eventually generate an appeal, an increased motivation for participation." FG Portugal	1

Teacher benefits	Validation	Processes or criteria used to ensure the credibility and effectiveness of educational projects or methods.	"... value for myself, personal value and value for the school." FG Portugal	3
	Turnkey approach	Ready-to-implement, pre-designed resources or methods that teachers can use directly without extensive preparation.	"I'd like to pick up on what's just been said. It's very fair, I think, in relation to everything we've already got to do, it's true that starting a new project is always complicated, you always have to give up something, and a turnkey approach is also really really nice, it's a clear guarantee of practical applicability." FG France	7
	Kits and resources	Educational materials, tools, and kits provided to support project-based and hands-on learning experiences.	"Then, the famous kits or resources here, perhaps less necessary. I don't know exactly how they are thinking about the project, but it is important that people have everything they need to contribute to the project, from an APP on their cell phone to something more analog, physical, which is also one of the typically successful elements for encouraging participation. And then they can stay in schools and continue until they have access." FG Portugal	2
Student Benefits	Student Motivation and science interest	Initiatives to spark students' curiosity in science and motivate them to explore scientific topics actively.	"At least it motivates their interest. Since students are comfortable with digital tools, if we can spend a little time, they do it quickly in the classroom. And that is a satisfactory stimulus for something more." FG Greece	3
	Student Collaboration	Encouraging students to work together in groups, fostering teamwork, and communication skills.	"Obviously, there are scientists, research laboratories, other spaces, and other contexts that are often not those that appear in so-called non-citizen science projects. I think that this can also be an aspect that makes the project appealing, that is, I can have scientists who are more involved in schools. Teachers and students can also go to universities and research centers. I think that this permeability that is created in the citizen science project, with other spaces and other interlocutors, should also be an element that should be put on the table and that may eventually generate an appeal, an increased motivation for participation." FG France	9

Student Benefits	Students call to action and environmental awareness	Activities or projects aimed at empowering students to act on environmental issues and raise awareness within their communities.	"They also have to have a critical attitude and be active citizens, fighting for what they think is best for the planet." FG Portugal	7
Negative Factors	Time Constraints	Limitations on time available due to the curriculum or class schedules, affecting project feasibility.	"Also, when it comes to carrying out these things, we want to carry them out, but if we are presented with a didactic sequence of 20 sessions, then of course, well, I said 20 sessions, perhaps an outrageous..." FG Spain	25
	Lack of Resources	Insufficient materials, funding, or other resources that hinder effective participation or project execution.	"So, those who are responsible for the project often don't even provide the support they should to those who are on the ground implementing the project. That's half the battle to ensure things don't go well. There are always doubts to ask. There are always obstacles to overcome." FG Portugal	5
	Lack of Training and Knowledge	Inadequate teacher or student preparation, affecting their ability to effectively engage with the project or curriculum content.	"As Participant 4 says, they are going to sneak in things that we don't know. Well, it's obvious that they're going to sneak it in because if you don't know about economics, you don't know about certain things, it's easy for them to sneak it in. In fact, when there is some fake news like this that comes out, you start searching and it is in all the media, in all the newspapers because they have published it. Then you will always give it more truth, even if it is not." FG Spain	9
	Curriculum Fit	Challenges in aligning project content and objectives with the existing curriculum requirements.	"...or if it is not interconnected with the content and the teachers do not think it is useful" FG Portugal	7
	Increasing of workload	Additional demands placed on teachers' time and responsibilities willing to implement new projects.	"I don't know how many colleagues are interested in doing something more than what their formal duties require." FG Greece	10

Negative Factors	Goals not clear	Uncertainty about the project's objectives, such as whether it focuses on critical thinking, environmental issues, or media literacy.	"Because I think there is a lot of newness here and the idea is that I will get some news once a month. Is it as many as I want? During what interval? In other words, how will all this happen from a temporal point of view? I think that not being clear to me would also lead me to not participate." FG Portugal	9
	Complexity	Professional development sessions aimed at building teacher and student competencies specific to project needs.	"Another resounding "no" could be the complexity of the project, which could compromise its feasibility and increase the time it would take. Something too bold. Bold doesn't mean megalomaniac, does it?" FG Portugal	2
Ideas	Workshops	Training sessions designed to provide practical knowledge and skills, often involving hands-on activities.	"I think a good idea, which was mentioned earlier, is the skill workshops, which are essentially taken on by individuals who are interested, there is no specific curriculum for the teacher to cover, there are only some activities." FG Greece	7
	Digital tools	Use of technology and software to enhance learning and project implementation.	"But at the same time to suggest some digital tools. There are new interactive boards. From the new year, there will be boards in all schools, which are very helpful for digital material to enter the classroom. And I have seen nice applications, always digital, from some platforms, which are not necessarily educational, that is, not E-Class." FG Greece	9
	Cross-disciplinary approach	Integration of multiple subjects or areas of knowledge within a single project to provide a holistic learning experience.	"I think it was important for it to be interdisciplinary to be part of the class council. Maybe that was it." FG Portugal	10
	"Factcheckers"	Resources or tools used to verify information accuracy, promoting media literacy and critical evaluation.	"Yes, it occurs to me as a kind of contest for "fact checkers", what they call now, those who are dedicated... those who verify the facts, that it be a contest to search for fake news and verify it themselves." FG Spain	6
Motivational Factors	Personal Interest	Teacher's intrinsic motivation and enthusiasm for topics related to global awareness, citizenship, or environmental issues.	"Well, sorry, but I think we all like personal and professional recognition. I mean, we don't work on this for the sake of it either. Therefore, we often give a lot of ourselves and receive practically no recognition, so I think it is definitely important to recognize the work of teachers." FG Portugal	2

Motivational Factors

Professional Development	Opportunities for teachers to expand their skills and grow professionally through project participation.	"I think it's essentially the behind-the-scenes work of the project, in the sense that I can also help them and empower them with this fact-checking , with this critical capacity that they use today in the project, but tomorrow in daily life - a news story comes out and perhaps I feel more capable of understanding that it might not be as true as I thought it was." FG Portugal	2
Student Impact	Expected or observed positive effects of the project on students' attitudes, skills, or academic performance.	"I think the biggest motivation for us (I have many years of service - I don't have many personal ambitions) for us classroom teachers is if the children make a leap, even a small one, in relation to this... the routine of education, because their joy is very great, very great." FG Greece	5
Community Impact	Potential or actual positive contributions of the project to the local community, fostering engagement and support.	"This way, the Municipality can connect some schools in a common effort. Because if we stay only in small groups (at the school level) the impact will be small." FG Greece	2
Recognition and Rewards	Formal acknowledgment or incentives provided for participation, which can motivate teachers and students.	"And there are several common points here in projects that I see as successful. Many times they have gifts for the school or for the teachers. Gifts are not monetary gifts. But there are kits or something like that that are given to schools that help and encourage this participation. And that make the people who are participating think: "This is cool, we win a weather station or we win something for the school". This is something that motivates teachers, because then we stop thinking only about ourselves and the class itself and think about the school as a whole, which is also important." FG Portugal	6
Collaboration Opportunities	Possibilities for teamwork and partnerships with other teachers, experts, or organizations that enhance project outcomes.	"It can multiply only if some schools cooperate. The children get to know each other in the same areas this way. We also reduce the rivalry between schools because we have cooperation groups." FG Greece	5

Motivational Factors	Student Engagement and Motivation	Observable enthusiasm and sustained interest among students, promoting active participation in the project.	"...the routine of education, because their joy is very great, very great." FG Greece	3
Needs	Workshops and training	Opportunities for training and professional growth related to the project.	"An initial training..." FG Spain	4
	Flexibility	Adaptability of scheduling and requirements, allowing adjustments to fit participants' availability and needs.	"What would interest me is for it not to focus on a specific age or level, because as we have to choose a course on September 1, maybe you are looking forward to taking the third year of ESO to do the project and then there is no God who organizes it and they don't let you third in ESO or whatever, so..." FG Spain	4
	Resource Availability	Access to necessary materials, funding, and other resources essential for project implementation.	"It motivates me, if you give me the work done, if you give me the materials, you give me the didactic list of how to organize myself and so on, everything you do for me motivates me a lot." FG Spain	1
Time Availability	Positive Availability		"Yes, and I, on a personal level, within the school framework, could dedicate time." FG Greece	6
	2h-6h	Time commitment category indicating projects that can be completed within a range of 2 to 6 hours/sessions.	"If it is in general subjects, I think that, about 6 sessions, would be fine." FG Spain	6
	6-10h	Time commitment category for projects requiring between 6 and 10 hours/sessions.	"I think it's a maximum, yes, about ten hours." FG France	7
Conditions	Doesn't have a proper timeframe	Lack of a defined timeline.	"If you ask me objectively how much time, I have no idea." FG Portugal	3
	School Curriculum	Takes into account the school curriculum requirements.	"think it depends. Imagine that the project aligns very objectively with a certain content of essential learning. I could probably spend more time in that area. But if it were further away, I might not spend as much time. I don't know if I'm making myself clear." FG Portugal	2

Conditions	School Calendar	Takes into account the academic calendar, which dictates the available time and scheduling for project activities.	"But don't leave it until June either. This should end May at the beginning of May, mid-May." FG Spain	1
	Flexibility of project schedule	Ability to adjust the project timeline within the school year to accommodate various needs.	"Flexibility, I think. Because otherwise, if we're going to do something very rigidly, then it will work in one context, but in another you'll completely stumble, and so I would say that maybe that's the best option." FG Portugal	4
	School and Student Context	External factors, such as internet access, may influence project feasibility and student participation.	"A class that's more resistant to this kind of project, even if we bring all our conditioning to it, well, it's going to be a project that's just as complicated to run on your own when the class isn't necessarily ready to get involved." FG France	9
Time Commitment	Short-term	Projects designed to be compact and completed within a brief time frame.	"...having sessions that are rather short in relation to the audience I have." FG France	5
	Long-term	Projects spread out over an extended period, providing more in-depth exploration and engagement.	"I think that the idea here is also to train them as citizens, so something that's a bit more long term can also be interesting" FG France	5
School terms	1st term	Projects initiated early in the school year, typically during the first academic term.	"If it's a project that can be presented fairly early in the year, even if it's not completely finished, i.e. not necessarily on the first day of term, but quickly enough to tell the pupils that we're going to take part in a project, whereas if it comes at the start of the year, the risk is that it'll come as a bit of a bolt from the blue." FG France	3
	3rd term	Projects scheduled toward the end of the academic year, during the third term.	"it would be more effectively around the month of May" FG France	1
Solution	Cross-disciplinary	Approach allowing integration	"if you want to propose it as being interdisciplinary between	6

		across multiple subjects, promoting a broader understanding of the project theme.	several subjects, because maybe it is easier to put in more hours, which we told you before. Well, if I want to work on climate change and from language they work on reading the news, from biology, the search for reliable information, if they are working on a biology topic or if it is climate change, I can focus on how it affects the species in physics and chemistry..." FG Spain	
Solution	Project classes	Specific classes that have the flexibility to incorporate project-based learning, such as science or digital literacy classes.	"I just wanted to add that I hear what people are saying about the programme, but I find that we have a certain amount of flexibility, especially in the digital teaching or perhaps even in scientific teaching, with a very broad curriculum and above all certification objectives at the end of the year. So we're not necessarily obliged to complete the programme, we have greater freedom, which would allow us to see if by adjusting the hours, if we could increase the volume of hours a little for example, we could be more comfortable with these levels." FG France	3
	Detailed project timeframe	A clear, structured timeline outlining project milestones and deadlines.	"as long as it was perfectly organized with the respective director, the hours, the sessions, the objectives of the sessions and what specific work, I think it would be perfectly possible to integrate it." FG Portugal	5
	Task-motivated and not time motivated	Emphasis on completing tasks rather than focusing on the time spent, encouraging efficient and goal-oriented work.	"Therefore, I would never risk putting things like this, too much restricted in X classes or X hours for this and hours for that, but in very specific tasks, with very careful monitoring and knowing that I have delivery points here. Small reports , anyway, not things that are not mobilizing, because no one is up for that either, but I would not commit to specific times, more to tasks to be completed, I would say." FG Portugal	2
Problems	Preparation time	Required time for teachers and students to prepare for the project, including planning and gathering resources.	"but quickly enough to tell the pupils that we're going to take part in a project, whereas if it comes at the start of the year, the risk is that it'll come as a bit of a bolt from the blue. The idea is that, well, it's an extra burden, whereas if it's part of the initial contract, it'll probably go down a bit better, and then maybe it'll be an end in itself." FG France	1

Problems	Students Openess to the project	The willingness and receptivity of students to engage in new projects or approaches.	"Regarding time outside of class, in a secondary school context I don't think students would spend much time. That's what I think. They wouldn't spend much time outside of class." FG Portugal	5
	Project methods and timeframe	Defined strategies and scheduling methods tailored to project requirements.	"think that yes, yes, that it is important to take into account a little, to see a little of the deadlines that are going to be available. Precisely to know how to develop it and even, when programming the subject, you can make the pertinent changes if they can be made, not in such a way that says well look..." FG Spain	6
	Exams and orals	Academic assessments like exams and oral presentations, which may impact or coincide with project timelines.	"I'm going to do it maybe a bit earlier in the year, around April at the latest, because then they're revising, they've got exams, they've gone on to other things like the Grand Oral" FG France	3
Project Design	Theoretical/practice based	Balance between theoretical content and hands-on activities within the project.	"It has a lot to do with the nature of the project. If it is a more theoretical project, it will be very difficult to find volunteers to collaborate. If it is a more practical project, I think people will join in more easily." FG Portugal	1
Resources and Support	Resource availability	Availability of necessary materials, equipment, and funding for project success.	"but sometimes some financing is considered if necessary. In other words, "I have to leave or the school has to invite someone and I have no way of bringing them or I have no way of renting a bus". Anyway, I don't know if this is considered here, possibly not, but if some kind of expense is considered for the school or some kind of expense that the school has to cover, of course it won't come from the school's budget, which is usually very tight. I don't know if the project here would also have some way of accommodating some situations or at least, at the outset, considering this possibility" FG Portugal	1
Teacher	Training	Instructional sessions for teachers or students to build relevant skills for effective project participation.	"I give the training to us. Well, we have finished saying it now, but without some training sessions on the project first, it is difficult." FG Spain	1

Other suggestions	Scientific Production indicators	Metrics such as publications or presentations used to measure and reward academic contributions within the project.	"I think that the point here to catch universities has to be also through some aspect of scientific productivity indicators. For me, this can of course be publications in the didactic, pedagogical field, etc. Great, but something has to come out of it, otherwise it will be very difficult to convince them in the end on this issue." FG Portugal	1
	Rewards and recognition	Incentives or formal acknowledgment that serve as motivation for schools, teachers, and students involved in the project.	"Just one more thing here or there. I think it would be important to make the rewards a little clearer to schools. Of course, there is always the educational reward of learning, obviously, that is transversal. But something more tangible. In other words, what do I get in return? In addition to all this, which is transversal to any educational project, what does this school gain? Anyway, will there be a competition? A contest for something more visible? A report that is done at the school? Anything that gives visibility and that they feel, I am being rewarded and I am feeling recognized for what I did." FG Portugal	2
	Motivation throughout	Sustained enthusiasm and interest from students and teachers throughout the project duration.	"Sometimes there are those declines and also think about those moments to get back to having some more motivational input. Maybe even going to schools or doing something. Because this is also an aspect of citizen science, which is that we start without any strength and then we go with all the energy, but then we fall again and I think the team has to be prepared to seize this participation and to stimulate it in a more effective way." FG Portugal	1

c. How to make the project appealing

Here participants were asked to give their ideas on how to make this project appealing and useful for teachers:

School context. The project must be implemented at school rather than independently, as each student has very different realities outside of school. You can, for example, use the science clubs at each school as promoting-agents of the initiative. In addition, bridges must be established with universities, researchers and journalists outside the school. It can also be inserted into existing skills workshops, which promote creative activities. Finally, kits and materials (both analogue and digital) must be provided for the school that is developing the project. The school's board of directors must be involved in the project and recognize its importance by supporting it and making the work of the teachers involved more flexible. For example, protocols can be established with schools where the project gives training and resources to teachers, and the project headquarters provides more time and attention.

Fact checker initiatives. Create an initiative within the project, where a repository of fake news is created and then a kind of competition is held to detect them. This would give the students the tools to be able to identify them and to understand the amount of misinformation that exists around them. The focus of the news would be on climate change and other environmental problems.

Multidisciplinary and inclusive work. There should be an involvement of the teachers' council in the project so that the tasks are distributed multidisciplinary across several topics and several teachers. The project will be much richer if it is a single learning project across several subjects, including first language and foreign language courses. Moreover, having more teachers and subjects involved would provide more time to be dedicated to the project, ensuring a more comprehensive approach.

Usefulness and belonging. The project must be aligned with the learning and curricular objectives defined by the Ministry of Education and international objectives such as the SDGs. It is essential that teachers feel that the project is practical, easy to implement and integrated and that it is not just

additional work (e.g. citizen science projects where there is co-construction of scientific knowledge and recognition of the work of teachers and students).

Use of digital tools and social networks. Use interactive tools and applications, such as QR codes and questionnaires, in the classroom, which allow interaction and immediate responses from students. This strategy would allow quick content to be created that fits more easily into the school schedule. In addition to these applications, social networks such as YouTube as a tool and source of information were also highlighted.

Collaborative aspect. There is the possibility of various levels of involvement, and people can decide how they want to get involved in the project.

Valuation of the project. One important thing is for students to feel that they are part of something meaningful, where their work contributes to solving a bigger problem, rather than addressing a local issue. Furthermore, the project will have much greater participation and more visibility within the school itself and in the local and national media; this gives recognition for the teachers' work. It is important to value the European dimension and promote the exchange of experiences between countries.

Workshops and courses. Training courses (e.g. Massive Open Online Course) for the teachers to provide tools to detect, teach and fight against fake news.

cd. Constraints and Motivations

When confronted with the of their participation in the project, more than one-third **main constraints** of the speeches refer to . Time is essential: it cannot be a project that takes too many **time constraints** hours. In line with this limitation, we asked how many hours the teachers could, realistically, dedicate to such a project in classes or school activities. In general, the responses were apprehensive and vague, pointing out that it depends on different variables like school context, alignment with the curricular

goals, number of students, time of the year, and the courses. In the Greek and the Portuguese focus groups, these fears were accompanied by the suggestion of creating a flexible schedule, without established hours, but with schedules and deadlines, to accomplish concrete tasks. The teachers in the French group unanimously agreed they could spend 10 hours. Lastly, the Spanish group pointed out the ideal time to be 5 or 6 hours.

The other big constraint was the (mental and physical) that left teachers in a **increasing workload** defensive posture. This cannot be just another project and more extra work. Also, it cannot be very complex and challenging to implement - it's essential to have materials and content ready to use, and to establish all the goals at the beginning of the curricular year.

Other mentioned constraints were the lack of training on detecting fake news and the **lack of resources to implement the project** .

On the bright side, when asked about their **motivations** for participating with the project, the participants enumerated the following aspects:

- **Creation of new connections and networks with academia, researchers and journalists.**
- **Contribute to increase the visibility and recognition of their country - "Possibility of putting Portugal on the map".**
- **Production of real outputs (e.g. scientific papers).**
- **Developing critical and scientific thinking skills in the students that increasingly believe in social networks and influencers more than teachers.**
- **Recognition of the teachers' work by the school management and peers; added value for students, teachers and schools.**
- **Support from the project team of specialists in this field of knowledge.**
- **Certification and credit given by the project.**
- **Provide schools with tools, outputs and content (kits).**

FUTURE CONSIDERATIONS AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR IMPROVEMENT

Throughout this project, we encountered several **positive outcomes** that deserve to be highlighted.

The decision to conduct the focus groups sessions online enabled the participation of teachers from diverse locations, whether from urban, semi-urban or rural areas, and educational contexts. This allowed for a greater variety of opinions and realities, thereby strengthening the robustness of our results.

Another key positive aspect was the flexibility afforded by the online format, which minimized logistical challenges, reduced time constraints, and allowed more participants to join, even those with busy schedules. Moreover, considering an environmental and sustainability perspective, the online format dismissed the need for travel, thus supporting an eco-friendlier approach to data collection, aligning with the climate-conscious goals inherent to this international project. Reinforcing, once more, the shared commitment among all teams involved in the project to uphold sustainability measures and to prioritize environmental responsibility throughout all process.

Developing and giving access to a standardized guide for all moderators was crucial to ensure, as much as possible, a methodological consistency across different countries. This approach not only facilitated a more unified process but also reinforced the reliability of the findings. Additionally, this method also helps moderators feel more secure and comfortable while leading these sessions, as they are equipped with a clear framework.

Building on the success of the results gathered, we have identified to further **key opportunities** enhance the ease of cohesion and collaboration within countries, as well as to improve data analysis and quality in future initiatives. In particular:

- **Focus Group Workshop for Moderators**

Some discrepancies among focus groups were noticed during data analysis, making data comparison challenging and, consequently, data quality compromised. For example, ensuring that all questions are answered clearly and by all participants is a detail that improves data analysis and categorization. To address these issues, we believe that a short workshop for moderators would help standardize practices in future sessions. In addition, this approach will promote a more consistent methodology, promote equal footing among moderators, and address the different contexts among countries. By aligning all moderators, we would improve the consistency of focus group analyses, further connect teams and further elevate the quality of our qualitative analysis results.

- **Rethinking Questions Structure**

To ensure the quality and consistency of participants’

perspectives and insights into future projects, we would suggest structuring questions to be more closed-ended and direct. This approach would enhance various stages of the project and make its analysis more efficient:

- a.** Facilitate moderators work, as closed-ended questions reduce the possibility of responses diverging from the main topics of interest, reducing moderators’ efforts of keeping participant’s focused;
- b.** Facilitate data analysis, simplifying the ability to draw cohesive insights from the testimonies provided;
- c.** **More focused participants**, as direct questions make it clear to participants of the goal at hand, helping them to stay on topic.

- **Dedicated Focus Groups for Teachers and Teacher Trainers**

While our results gave us rich insights and perspectives from both groups (teacher and teacher trainers), separating them into distinct focus groups would allow for even richer, more focused insights into each group’s

experiences. In addition, focus groups with homogeneous groups of participants may also stimulate the discussions. Adopting this format would enable more targeted and relevant questions, leading to higher-quality data and, consequently, even stronger results.

- **The Importance of Physical Language**

While the variety of languages imposes some barriers in understanding one another, physical language - such as gestures and mannerisms - serves as a universal form of communication, helping to interpret the intent behind each participant's remarks and ideas. In order to support future focus groups involving several countries, we recommend to ask/obtain the proper authorizations to record the focus group sessions in video format. Making these recordings accessible to the researchers conducting content analysis would allow for the interpretation of non-verbal cues, facilitating a more robust analysis and help reducing the barriers imposed by the usage of different languages.

Through the integration of these improvements in future focus groups, we can advance even more towards excellence, reinforcing both the quality of results and the spirit of cooperation and networking within countries.

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Appendix 1

1. General guidelines for the organization of the focus group

Length: 45 to 90 minutes duration (tell participants beforehand that this will be a 1½ -2-hour event).

Date, time and location: choose an accessible location (or zoom if it is considered a good option); when deciding we should take care to reduce barriers for the participants.

If needed: obtain university ethics approval (all partners need to check the need for it and the timings)

Number of questions: 8 [script below].

Number of participants: 6 (4 teachers and 2 teacher trainers) [each partner should create a participants file].

Participant profile: see below the teacher profile.

2. Participants profile

2 teacher trainers (can be University Professors teaching in Pedagogical Departments (undergraduate or postgraduate) or teachers who are qualified to act as teachers' trainers," or they might work as freelancers in training teachers in such teachers' training programs (run by private or public institutions).

4 in service teachers with 5-10 years' experience.

9th grade (natural sciences: biology, geology/geography, physics and chemistry).

10th, 11th, 12th grade (for the scientific branch only: biology, geology/geography, physics and chemistry)

Gender equality and diversity.

Accept climate change as a fact, criterion for inclusion "We would you to participate in a focus group, do you accept climate change".

3. Documents needed

Moderator script with set and lining of questions [created English and each partner translates to each language].

Information to the participant (created English and should be adapted according to rules of each institution).

Consent form (should be prepared according to rules of each institution).

Documents required for ethics approval in each country (each partner prepares according to needs).

Letter of invitation — to be prepared in English.

4. Organizational checklist

Before the meeting

- Decide location.
- Decide date.
- Recruit/invite participants (and confirm participation; count with a no-show).
- Arrange for snacks and drinks (if in person).
- Arrange for compensation/incentive.
- Choose moderator.
- Choose co-moderator (recording, taking notes on subtle tips, zoom support if zoom).
- Review script with moderators.
- Decide on the recording procedure.
- Print consent forms [do we need university ethical approval, how much time does it take?].
- Get name tags (or number tags if needed for confidentiality).

On the day

- Arrive early / set call early.
- Set space forms and number tags [to anonymize from start].
- Start 15 minutes after schedule time: on arrival people sign in consent form, put on number tags, have snacks.
- Make sure you record when you start.
- Introductory remarks: Explain purpose, who you are, confidentiality.
- Review ground rules.
- Ask questions without leading or responding (Prompt for clarifications, spelling, etc.).
- Wrap up.
- Thank participants and share the next steps.

Immediately after session

- Moderator and co-moderator debrief immediately with key thoughts.
- Write up session notes within 24 hours if necessary.

After session

- Prepare report (in English).
- Send report to ICNOVA team.

Appendix 2

SchoolFAN focus groups

Section	Topic and questions	Suggestions
<p>Welcome/introduction</p> <p>5 minutes</p>	<p>Welcometheparticipants</p> <p>Present the moderator and co-moderator</p> <p>Explain the purpose of this focus group</p> <p>Review ground rules</p> <p>Anonymity</p>	<p>Thank youforagreeing to be part of this focus group.</p> <p>----</p> <p>This focus group is part of a project called SchoolFAN. We aim to develop a citizen science project on identifying and debunking fake news about climate change, for students from 9th to 12th grade. This would be done in schools in France, Greece, Spain and Portugal.</p> <p>The reason we are organizing this focus group is to ask for your input on addressing these topics in the classroom.</p> <p>We would like everyone to participate. There are no right or wrong answers: every opinion is important. You can agree with others, disagree, and build on others' positions. The only two rules are to be respectful towards others and to keep on the subject of the question. Sometimes I, as the moderator, may have to interrupt some of you to make sure everybody contributes, and I will apologize already for this.</p> <p>The session is recorded, so we do not miss any information, but will not identify anyone in the</p>

		report. This session will be transcribed by removing any information that may identify you, your institution or students. It will afterwards be translated to English and analyzed for the purposes of the project and to publish an academic paper.
Icebreaker 10 minutes	<p>Ask the participants to present themselves with name and surname and the subject they teach.</p> <p>(can add “and what do you like to do in your free time” if you feel would make them at ease).</p>	The moderator can be the first to answer the icebreaker question if there is one.
Engagement questions (to introduce participants to and make them comfortable with the topic of discussion) 10 minutes	<p>1- Do you think the curriculum/programs of your discipline empower students to be critical about the information they consume? Why and how?</p>	
Exploration questions (suggestion: max 15 minutes in each, and not going over one hour)	<p>Our project aims to empower the students to identify and debunk fake news about climate change.</p> <p>2 - Do you know any examples of addressing fake news in your classes? If yes, can you please describe how and based on what curricular goals? If not, why?</p> <p>3 - Do you know any examples of addressing climate change in your classes? If yes, can you please describe how and based on what</p>	<p>Remember to make sure everyone contributes, make eye contact with all to see if someone wants to speak</p> <p>Use flipchart/ post-its in board to summarize the thoughts?</p>

curricular goals? If not, why?

4- From your experience, what points in the curriculum of your disciplines do you think addressing fake news related to climate would fit well? And in which grades are these?

Within our project, we wish to implement, with teachers' participation, a citizen science project where the students debunk fake news about climate change.

Citizen science is where non academic scientists contribute to scientific research.

You may be already familiar with some citizen science projects, for example: e-bird, iNaturalist (moderators find locally relevant ones)

In the development of this project, we will provide training and training materials on citizen science and on debunking fake news for the teachers.

5- How do you think we can make this citizen science project appealing and useful for teachers? Do you have any other ideas?

6 - What do you feel would prevent you and what would motivate you to participate in a project like this?

	<p>7 - How much time do you think you would be willing to dedicate to such a project in your classes or school activities, realistically?</p>
<p>Exit questions</p> <p>(check to see if anything was missed in the discussion)</p>	<p>8 - Is there anything else that you feel we should pay attention to in our project?</p>
<p>Wrap up and next steps</p>	<p>Thank you so much for your participation and for this nice conversation.</p> <p>This will be very important for the development of this project</p> <p>We will be sharing our advances in our webpage and social media.</p> <p>Thank you!</p>